

Teacher Effectiveness of Women Student Teachers in Relation to Their Adjustment

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ABSTRACT

Education develops man's faculty, specially his mind so that he may be able to enjoy the contemplation of supreme truth, goodness and beauty. Education plays a vital role in the programme of nation building. The most powerful instruments to meet the challenge of poverty and deprivation and of the widening gap between the rich and the poor among countries are education and research. The present study aims at investigating the teacher effectiveness of women student teachers in relation to their adjustment. For the purpose of investigation, descriptive survey the method was employed. A random sample of 600 women student teachers was drawn from Colleges of Education few affiliated to north Karnataka Akkamahadevi Women's University. The tools used for the present study include Teacher Effectiveness Scale developed by Umme Kulsum, Adjustment Scale Constructed and standardized by Dr. S. K. Mangal. There were used for the collection of data. The statistical techniques such as Mean, SD and t values co-efficient of correlation Two way ANOVA, Regressions analysis, Path analysis were applied. The teacher effectiveness of differential between married and unmarried adjustment teachers are also found positively different. This paper studied the problem related to student teachers. Every research leaves new scope and opens new ideas for further study. Accordingly the researcher hopes that readers of this paper will be benefited in developing insight me the field of teacher education.

Key words: Teacher Effectiveness, Adjustment

INTRODUCTION

"Education is the influence of the environment on the individual with a view to bring out permanent change in his behavior of thought and of attitude"

- Thompson.

Education has always been accorded an honored place in Indian society. Great many people have stressed the fundamental role of education and its unique significance for national development. 'Education' is a complex concept. It may refer to formal schooling or to the life long process of learning from experiences. It has been variously viewed as acquisition of

knowledge (attitudes & skills), transmission of culture, drawing out and developing the best potential, disciplining, moulding the personality and liberation. Gandhi felt strongly that education must reintegrate the individual and develop him as a member of a living society. The aim is to inculcate in the child a spirit of co-operation and sense of responsibility from the very beginning. Education, as a social function, is the social process. The education of a child is possible in a social environment. Through this social process the mature members of the society pass on their own experience, interest,

purpose, attitude and disposition to the immature members of the society.

Every one alive has troubles and problems, the most important consideration in determining personal effectiveness is not the amount of trouble or misfortune (within limits) a person encounters, but how he responds or adjust to the challenges of life. Horney suggested a major level of effort which men employ to bring into his life integration of all of the opposing forces he meets in dealing with people. These major levels of efforts; major adjustment techniques will be are moving toward, people moving against people and moving away from people.

Teachers occupy a pivotal position in any progressive society. Whether viewed as a model, a director, a supervisor, a guide, or a leader, the task of a teacher is crucial in moulding the youth. They become contributing individuals of the society. Philosophers, psychologists and great leaders of the twenty first century have highlighted the significance of the role of a teacher in the society, and the part he plays directly or indirectly in the building up of a nation. During 1966, the late president of India, Dr. S. Radhakrishnan observed that the teacher's place in the society is of vital importance. He acts as a pivot for the transmission of intellectual traditions, and technical skill, from generation to generation, and helps to keep the lamp of civilization burning. He not only guides the individual, but also to say directs him toward the destiny of the nation.

A teacher is not just a mere passenger of information, he is more than that. Apart from performing the role of teacher he should be in such a position to guide and understand his/her students emotions, feelings and able to have supportive relationship. For this he should have teacher effectiveness and have better knowledge for his/her i.e. adjustment.

Prospective-teachers are those who are undergoing training or studying in B.Ed. course become teachers and they are known by different names like 'would be teachers',

'pupil teachers', 'teacher-trainees', 'student-teachers', and 'future-teachers'

1. DEFINITIONS OF IMPORTANT TERMS USED

Teacher Effectiveness

The term 'Teacher Effectiveness' refers to the degree of success of a teacher in performing instructional, and other duties specified in his contract, and demanded by the nature of his position. The scores obtained by a teacher on "An Index of Teacher Effectiveness" is taken as the score for the variable teacher effectiveness. Here for each item in the index, the investigator rates the teacher while observing his/her performance in the actual teaching-learning situation in a classroom.

Adjustment

Adjustment is the process by which a living organism a balances between its need and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs.

Adjustment is a continual process by which a person varies his behavior to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the Teacher Effectiveness of the women student teachers in relation to their adjustment.
2. To compare the teacher effectiveness and adjustment of the married and unmarried women student teacher training colleges

HYPOTHESES:

Research Hypothesis 1: The married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges do not differ with respect to Teacher effectiveness and adjustment.

Research Hypothesis 2: The married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges do not differ in their adjustment.

Research Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference due to the combined effect of independent variables of

adjustment of married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges on teacher effectiveness scores.

Research Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in direct and indirect effect of adjustment of women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges on teacher effectiveness scores.

METHOD

The researcher employed descriptive survey research method of research for the present study.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

A random sample of 600 women student teachers was drawn from Colleges of Education affiliated to Akkamahadevi Women's University for the present study.

TOOLS OF THE STUDY: The tools used in the present study

1. Teacher Effectiveness Scale constructed and standardized by Umme Kulsum.

2. Teacher Adjustment Scale Constructed and standardized by Dr. S. K. Mangal,

PROCEDURE:

The women student teachers studying in different Colleges of Education were consulted. They were briefed about the study and its relevance Permission was obtained by the Principals of B.Ed Colleges. The tools were administered individually to the women student teachers and then data were collected.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The data collected were statistically analyzed by using measures of central tendency like Mean, Standard Deviation, t test and also by using Regression analysis and Path analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Mean,S,D and 't' values of married and unmarried women student teachers

Variable	Marital status	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Signi.
Teacher Effectiveness	Married	49.81	9.81	-5.2648	0.0001	S
	Unmarried	53.65	6.22			
Adjustment	Married	40.57	9.12	-2.7920	0.0054	S
	Unmarried	43.13	44.06			

Interpretation 1.1:

- The above Table 1 indicter that the married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges differ statistically significant with respect to their teacher effectiveness. The teacher effectiveness (M:53.65) of unmarried women student teachers is found to be more than teacher's effectiveness of married

women student teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Because of this, it is concluded as follows:

- Conclusion 1.1: the unmarried women student teachers do have better and significant teacher effectiveness as compared to married women student teachers.

Table 2: Correlation and 't' values of teacher effectiveness and adjustment scores of married and unmarried and women student teachers

Variable Adjustment	Correlation between teacher effectiveness scores of married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges				
	n	df	r-value	t-value	p-value
Married	116	114	0.8981	21.8066	0.0001,S
Unmarried	484	482	0.9255	53.6571	0.0001, S

Interpretation 2.1:

- The Table 2 shows that that the married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges differ statistically significant with

respect to their adjustment. that is, it is found that adjustment of unmarried women student teachers is found to be more than teacher's effectiveness of married women student teachers is more

(M=43.13) than the married women student teachers. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Because of this, it is concluded as follows:

- Conclusion 2.1: the unmarried women student teachers do have better and significant adjustment than the married women student teachers.

Table 3: Regression coefficient, standard error of regression coefficient and t of analysis of adjustment of married and unmarried women student teachers on teacher effectiveness scores

Independent variables Adjustment	Estimate	SE of Estimate	t-value	p-value	Signi
Constant	-1.0615	3.1857	-0.3332	0.7396	NS
Married	0.1279	0.1478	0.8654	0.3887	NS
Constant	9.3932	1.2622	7.4420	0.0001	S
Unmarried	0.1091	0.0064	17.0186	0.0001	S
R=0.9055, R ² =0.8200, F(4,111)=126.47 p<0.05, S Std.Error of estimate: 4.2369					
R=0.9425, R ² =0.8884, F(4,479)=953.41 p<0.05, S, Std.Error of estimate: 2.0873					

Interpretation 3.1:

- The combined influence of adjustment of married women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges on teacher effectiveness scores is found to be positive and significant at 5% level of significance. It means that, the on teacher effectiveness scores is influenced by adjustment of married and unmarried women student teachers

studying in teachers training colleges. Therefore, it is concluded on form the married women student teachers studying in teachers training college is affected by adjustment.

- Conclusion 4.1: The teacher effectiveness married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges are affects by adjustment.

Table 4: The Direct and indirect effect of adjustment of women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges on teacher effectiveness

Dependent variable	Independent variables	Direct effects	Indirect effects through
			Adjustment
Teacher effectiveness	Adjustment	0.1467*	-

Interpretation 4.1:

- The above Table 4 indicates that there is a direct effect of adjustment on teacher effectiveness women student teachers. it is found to be positive and significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded as follows:
- Conclusion 4.1: The adjustment of women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges directly affects teacher effectiveness.

- The unmarried women student teachers have better adjustment when compared with the married women student teachers.
- The teacher effectiveness of both married and unmarried women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges is affect by adjustment.
- The adjustment of women student teachers studying in teachers training colleges directly affects teacher effectiveness. It is also found that adjustment of teacher effectiveness of the women student teachers is positive and significant.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

The statistical analysis of results has research the following major findings:

- The unmarried women student teachers do have better and significant teacher effectiveness as compared to married women student teachers.

Education Implications

The Results of the present investigation give are indication that the teacher effectiveness of married and unmarried- women student teachers is affected by the factors such as

adjustment, self-concept, personality, emotional intelligence and other related factors in terms of their perceptions, interactions and expectations. Therefore, the present study recommends that both the married and unmarried teachers need to develop and possess basic teaching skill as a part of their repertoire of teaching effectiveness. In addition to this, pre-service training should be perceived and conceived seriously and then, it should help them to become effective teachers.

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How to cite this article: Patil SS, Kumar AGH. Teacher effectiveness of women student teachers in relation to their adjustment. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(2):241-245.
